

An advanced method of non-traditional bird skin preparation, to ease applications of scientific methods and enhance the value of avian collections

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Birds are among the oldest taxidermized animals, started with mummification as grave goods by Egyptians (Schulze-Hagen, Steinheimer et al. 2003, Wasef, Wood et al. 2015). The methods of preparation have changed, but not its value – be it for veneration, burial goods, art, or scientific research (Winker 2005, Ikram 2015). For the latter one birds are traditionally prepared with folded wings and a straight body, which has more historical than scientific reasons (Carrillo-Ortiz, Guallar et al. 2021). Despite every taxidermist has his own ‘handwriting’ which more specifically means, that even if the method of preparation remains the same the results will be different (e.g., stretched neck, elongated arms) and therefore measurements taken are already distorted. This type of preparation neglects correct scientific use of the object, as it impedes the interpretation of moult and key features e.g., for age identification. To be able to examine color patterns and moult correctly, wings should not be folded as on a traditionally prepared bird skins, where the correct determination of these parameters often causes unavoidable damage to the specimen. Another nowadays huge disadvantage, that is hardly mentioned, is that on ‘classic’ bird skins, that the skull, leg bones and distal ends of wing bones are usually left within the skin, even though they can provide crucial scientific data (Winker 2000, Tsai, Schedl et al. 2020). We want to advance the trend set by Norris (1961) of non-traditional bird skin preparation (Hendry 2016), a method which attempts to achieve maximum potential for future scientific use of avian collections. In addition, the digital recording, storage, and handling of the object was considered, to aim for further ease and precision in obtaining relevant information.

